

Synthesis and characterization of UO_2^{VI} , Th^{IV} , ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV} complexes with Schiff base derived from ethylene diamine/orthophenylene diamine and diacetyl monoxime

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Abstract : A series of complexes of the type $[\text{M}(\text{L})(\text{NO}_3)_2] \cdot m\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{SO}_4)] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where L is a Schiff base 1,10-dihydroxy-2,3,8,9-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraza-dec-1,3,7,9-tetraene (DHTTDT) or 5:6-benzo-1,10-dihydroxy-2,3,8,9-tetramethyl-1,4,7,10-tetraza-dec-1,3,7,9-tetraene (BDHTTDT) derived from ethylenediamine/*o*-phenylene diamine and diacetyl monoxime have been synthesized ($\text{M} = \text{ZrO}^{\text{IV}}$, UO_2^{VI} and Th^{IV} ; $m = 1, 2$ and 3 respectively). All the complexes are characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, thermal analysis, molar conductivity, magnetic moment, electronic, infrared, ^1H NMR and ESR spectral studies. The results indicate that the VO^{IV} ion is penta co-ordinated yielding paramagnetic complexes where as UO_2^{VI} , ZrO^{IV} ions are hexa co-ordinated and Th^{IV} ion is octa co-ordinated yielding diamagnetic complexes of above composition.

Keywords : Schiff base, electronic, infrared, ESR, ^1H NMR spectra.

Introduction

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of UO_2^{VI} , Th^{IV} , ZrO^{IV} and VO^{IV} complexes with Schiff base ligands synthesized from ethylene diamine/orthophenylene diamine and diacetyl monoxime.

Results and discussion

The complexes were formulated from the analytical data and molar conductance data support the suggested formulae (Table 1). The complexes are highly coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents such as ethanol, methanol, acetone, CCl_4 , CHCl_3 , benzene and ether but moderately soluble in highly coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. They are non-hygroscopic, highly stable under normal conditions and all of them decompose above 250°C . The molar conductance data values in DMSO for the complexes indicate them to be non-electrolyte in nature. However, the conductivity value is higher than as expected for non-electrolytes probably due to partial solvolysis of the complexes in DMSO medium¹.

IR spectra :

As the Schiff base ligand could not be isolated, the spectra of the complexes were compared with spectra of the starting materials and other related compounds. Ethylene diamine/orthophenylene diamine exhibit a pair of strong bands precisely located at ~ 3310 , ~ 3275 and $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be assigned to asymmetric, symmetric and deformation mode of vibration of NH_2 group respectively. Diacetyl monoxime exhibits strong band in the region $\sim 3350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to $\nu\text{N-OH}$. Apart from these a band system at $\sim 1620\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and 1720 cm^{-1} are observed in the above compound which may be attributed to azomethine $\nu\text{C=N}$ and carbonyl $\nu\text{C=O}$ vibration respectively². The IR spectra of the complexes show the following remarkable features :

The most notable features of the spectra is disappearance of νNH_2 , δNH_2 and $\nu\text{C=O}$ band but appearance of band at 1580 cm^{-1} in the complexes. The last band is due to azomethine $\nu\text{C=N}$ stretching vibration resulting from condensation of ethylene diamine/orthophenylene diamine with diacetyl monoxime. The position of the band is

Note

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Sl. No.	Compd.	Colour	μ_{eff}	Λ_m^a	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
					C	H	N	S	M
1.	[UO ₂ (DHTTDT)(NO ₃) ₂].2H ₂ O	Yellow	Dia.	21.26	18.96 (18.98)	3.42 (3.48)	13.25 (13.29)	-	37.62 (37.65)
2.	[UO ₂ (BDHTTDT)(NO ₃) ₂].2H ₂ O	Brownish yellow	Dia.	19.36	23.75 (23.79)	3.37 (3.39)	11.91 (11.89)	-	33.69 (33.71)
3.	[ZrO(DHTTDT)(NO ₃) ₂].H ₂ O	Daffodil	Dia.	33.56	24.41 (24.43)	4.45 (4.48)	17.09 (17.10)	-	18.52 (18.53)
4.	[ZrO(BDHTTDT)(NO ₃) ₂].H ₂ O	Daffodil	Dia.	33.12	31.32 (31.34)	4.07 (4.10)	15.65 (15.67)	-	16.95 (16.97)
5.	[Th(DHTTDT)(NO ₃) ₄].3H ₂ O	Pale cream	Dia.	32.11	15.77 (15.78)	3.13 (3.15)	14.71 (14.73)	-	30.49 (30.52)
6.	[Th(BDHTTDT)(NO ₃) ₄].3H ₂ O	Cream	Dia.	30.93	20.72 (20.74)	3.19 (3.20)	13.80 (13.82)	-	28.63 (28.64)
7.	[VO(DHTTDT)(SO ₄)].2H ₂ O	Black	1.80	18.34	28.21 (28.23)	5.14 (5.17)	13.11 (13.17)	7.48 (7.52)	12.3 (12.0)
8.	[VO(BDHTTDT)(SO ₄)].2H ₂ O	Chocolate	1.77	16.50	35.34 (35.36)	5.04 (5.05)	11.75 (11.78)	6.71 (6.73)	19.70 (19.73)

comparatively lower frequency region than usual $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ value which leads us to suggest that azomethine nitrogen atom has taken part in the complexation as evidenced from the appearance of bands in the region $\sim 480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu(\text{M}-\text{N})$. It is to be noted that though two $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ bands are expected due to their presence in different chemical environment, only one band due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ occurs in these complexes. The band due to $\nu\text{N}-\text{OH}$ intramolecularly H bonded continues to appear in the range 3250 cm^{-1} . Consequently the band occurring at $\sim 1250-1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu\text{C}-\text{N}$, in case of ligand containing orthophenylene diamine is blue shifted to 1490 cm^{-1} while that in case of ethylene diamine, it practically remains unaltered. This is because C-N assumes a partial double bond character on co-ordination to the metal ion through resonance in the former case.

The uranyl complexes exhibit a strong band at $\sim 955-910\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and the medium intensity band at $\sim 840-815\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to $\nu_{\text{as}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ and $\nu_{\text{s}}(\text{O}=\text{U}=\text{O})$ mode respectively³. The co-ordination of nitrate ions in unidentate manner has been indicated by the appearance of additional band at the region $\sim 1285\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1035\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the ν_2 and ν_4 modes of the vibration of co-ordinating nitrate ion under C_{2v}

symmetry⁴. The zirconyl complexes exhibit one strong band in the region $910-8650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which can be attributed to the $\nu(\text{Zr}=\text{O})$ as reported earlier⁵ indicating the presence of $(\text{Zr}=\text{O})^{2+}$ moiety in these complexes. In the oxovanadium polychelates strong bands at $\sim 955\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are assigned to $\nu(\text{V}=\text{O})$ modes⁶. However in vanadyl complexes, an additional series of four bands appeared at ~ 1120 , ~ 1035 , ~ 975 and $\sim 655\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the coordination of sulphate group in unidentate manner through oxygen atom⁷; the symmetry being lowered from T_D to C_{3v} upon coordination. Besides, the bands observed at $\sim 3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ of coordinated or lattice water. However all the complexes loss water when heated to $\sim 90\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ indicating the presence of lattice water molecules which has been confirmed by thermal analysis.

Thermal analysis :

All these complexes follow the same pattern of thermal decomposition. The complexes remain almost unaffected upto $\sim 50\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After this a slight depression upto $\sim 115\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ is observed. The weight loss at this temperature range is equivalent to one water molecule for zirconyl, two water molecules for uranyl and vanadyl and three water molecules for thorium(IV) complexes indicating them

to be lattice water in conformity with our earlier observations from analytical and IR spectral investigations. Once the lattice water was eliminated, the anhydrous complexes remain stable upto ~ 330 °C and thereafter the complexes show rapid degradation presumably due to decomposition of organic constituents of the complex molecules as indicated by the steep fall in the percentage weight loss. The decomposition continues upto ~ 715 °C and reaches to a stable product in each complexes as indicated by the consistency in weight in the plateau of the thermogram.

Electronic spectra :

The electronic spectra of the UO_2^{VI} complexes are quite similar. The complexes display mainly one weak band at ~ 460 nm and a highly intense band in the range 280–290 nm, which may be due to $^1\Sigma_g^+ \rightarrow ^3\Pi_u$ transitions and charge transfer transitions respectively⁸. It may be noted that the band occurring at 370 nm is due to uranyl moiety because of apical oxygen $\rightarrow f^0 (U)$ transition is being merged with the ligand band due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition as evident from broadness and intensity. The electronic spectra of ZrO^{IV} exhibit only one extra highly intensive band in the region 350–380 nm which may be due to charge transfer band besides the ligand bands. However, the electronic spectra could not provide structural details of these complexes. The electronic spectra of VO^{IV} complexes show three bands at ~ 12350 , ~ 18450 and ~ 25800 cm^{-1} corresponds to transitions, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{xz}d_{yz}(e)$, $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}(b_1)$ and $d_{xy}(b_2) \rightarrow d_{z^2}(a_1)$ respectively, indicating the complexes to be in distorted octahedral environment under C_{4v} symmetry⁹.

^1H NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectra of the complexes are recorded in $\text{DMSO}-d_6\text{-CDCl}_3$ medium. All the complexes show a sharp signal at δ 2.40–2.48 ppm corresponding to imine methyl ($\text{CH}_3\text{-C}=\text{N}$; 12H) protons. In DHTTDT complex an additional peak at 3.85 ppm is observed corresponding to 8 protons ($\text{NCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$). In BDHTTDT complexes a multiplet in the region 7.16–7.32 ppm is observed which may be assigned to aromatic ring protons. The proton signal due to oxime group $\text{>C}=\text{N-OH}$ is observed at δ 10.42 ppm in the NMR spectrum of the complexes indicating the presence of -OH via hydrogen bonding¹⁰.

ESR spectra :

The X-band ESR spectra of oxovanadium(IV) complexes are not so resolved at room temperature to exhibit all the eight hyperfine lines as expected for ^{51}V ($I=7/2$). The ESR spectra of the vanadium complex exhibited anisotropic signals in parallel and perpendicular ^{51}V region. The magnetic and bonding parameters deduced from the spectra are shown in Table 2. The covalency parameter α^2 as calculated from g_{\parallel} , g_{\perp} and A_{\parallel} values was found to be ~ 0.92 which suggests that these complexes have less covalent character in bonding involving the metal ion and ligand¹¹. The observed data show that g_{\parallel} and g_{\perp} values are closer to 2 and $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp}$. This suggests major distortion in the complexes from O_h symmetry.

Table 2. ESR spectral data of VO^{IV} complexes

Complexes	g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	A_{\parallel}	A_{\perp}	A_{av}	α^2
7	2.32	2.08	2.186	185	107	115.6	0.92
8	2.30	2.05	2.182	181	105	113	0.90

Materials and methods :

All the chemicals used of A.R. grade. The solvents were purified before use by standard procedures. As the Schiff base ligand isolation proved futile, all the metal complexes were synthesized *in situ* by taking different amount of metal salts, ethylene diamine/*o*-phenylene diamine and diacetyl monoxime.

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[M(\text{DHTTDT})(\text{NO}_3)_2].m\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $M = \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}}$, ZrO^{IV} , Th^{IV} and $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{SO}_4)].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

An ethanolic solution of hydrated metal nitrate/vanadyl sulphate (1 mmol) was added to a hot ethanolic solution of the mixture of ethylene diamine and diacetyl monoxime. The resulting mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 5–6 h during which a coloured complex was precipitated out in each case. It was filtered off, washed several times with ethanol followed by ether and finally dried *in vacuo* over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Preparation of the complexes of the type $[M(\text{BDHTTDT})(\text{NO}_3)_2].m\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $M = \text{UO}_2^{\text{VI}}$, ZrO^{IV} , Th^{IV} and $[\text{VO}(\text{L})(\text{SO}_4)].2\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

Same procedure was adopted for prepare

[M(BDHTTDT)(NO₃)₂].mH₂O and [VO(BDHTTDT)(SO₄)].mH₂O by taking orthophenylene diamine instead of ethylene diamine.

Estimation of uranium, zirconium, vanadium and thorium was done by known methods¹². Sulphur was estimated as BaSO₄ and nitrogen was estimated by Kjeldal method.

Room temperature magnetic susceptibilities were measured by Gouy method. The molar conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature with a Toshniwal conductivity Bridge (Model CL-01-06, cell constant 0.5 cm⁻¹) using 1 × 10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in DMSO. Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen contents of the complexes were estimated by using a MLW-CHN microanalyser. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Varian FTIR spectrophotometer, Australia. The electronic spectra of the complexes were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer* spectrophotometer. Thermo gravimetric analysis was done by Netzsch-429 thermoanalyser simultaneously recording of TG and DT curves at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹ in air. Around 50–100 mg of the sample was used in each case. The ¹H NMR spectra of the complexes were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ medium on JEOL GSX-400 model equipment. The ESR spectrum of the complex has only been recorded in solid state on Varian Associate spectrophotometer using 100 KHz, X-band (RT), scan range 2.0 × 1 KG and field set 3200.

Purity of these complexes were established by TLC on silica gel.

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